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Internal and External Competences of the EU in Migration Law

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The EU holds a range of competences in the area of migration. Over the past decades, the EU has developed a comprehensive constitutional framework that governs both internal migration across Member States of third-country nationals and external cooperation with third countries. While internal competences cover entry, residence, and asylum, external competences refer to its actions towards third countries concerning migration. The EU engages with countries of origin and transit through a range of measures, including partnership agreements and readmission arrangements. This may also be categorised as the internal and external dimension of migration law. This report outlines the development, scope, and limits of the EU's migration competences, focusing on EU-national relations, Treaty legal bases, and human rights obligations.

1 Development of EU Migration Competences

Due to the high political sensitivity of migration, the integration of this policy area at the EU level has progressed slowly. For many years, migration remained under the exclusive control of Member States, with the EU having mainly a supporting function.¹ While freedom of movement

¹ G Noll, 'Viciously Circular' in V Stoyana and S Smet (eds) *Migrants' Rights, Populism and Legal Resilience in Europe* (Cambridge University Press, 2022) 97; N El-Enany, 'EU Asylum and Immigration Law Under the AFSJ'

for EU citizens was established early, Member States still controlled the entry and residence of third-country nationals. Treaty reforms have changed the balance of power between the EU and national level. This section describes the development of EU competences in migration.

Under the Maastricht Treaty, migration lawmaking was confined to non-binding joint positions and international agreements that required ratification by national parliaments.² Governance was intergovernmental with minimal institutional involvement. Throughout this period – lasting into the 1990s – institutions such as the European Commission played only a limited role.³ Decision-making within the Council of the EU was based on unanimity, as each Member State had a de facto veto over migration proposals. This intergovernmental approach yielded few substantive legal outcomes.⁴ The Council primarily adopted non-binding resolutions addressing topics like unaccompanied minors, migrant workers, students, and refugee definitions.⁵ One significant milestone was the 1990 Dublin Convention, which laid the groundwork for Member State responsibility in asylum applications.⁶ While this governance model maximised national control, it significantly limited the EU’s capacity to act effectively on migration.

The Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) marked a turning point by incorporating migration in the EU’s supranational legal framework.⁷ It allowed for binding legislation in areas such as visas, asylum, and immigration.⁸ The Treaty also introduced the objective of creating an ‘area of freedom, security, and justice’. Nevertheless, Member States retained considerable power. The European Parliament only had the right to be consulted and did not yet share legislative power with the Council.⁹ The European Commission and the Member States jointly shaped the legislative agenda, and only the highest national courts could refer migration-related questions to the Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU). Unanimity in the Council was still required, further limiting supranational decision-making.¹⁰

The Treaty of Nice (2003) expanded qualified majority voting and strengthened the European Parliament’s role. It accelerated the shift towards greater EU competences in migration law. The Nice Treaty introduced qualified majority voting in the Council and granted the European Parliament co-decision powers in migration.¹¹

The Treaty of Lisbon (2009) further entrenched migration within EU law by formalising the area of freedom, security and justice and allowing lower national courts to make preliminary references to the CJEU. The number of cases referred to the CJEU increased significantly. While the CJEU only received 11 preliminary references from Member States between 2005 and 2009, it issued over 142 judgments in the decade that followed.¹²

in Arnall and Chalmers (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of European Union Law* (Oxford University Press, 2015) (2016) 869.

² D Thym, *European Migration Law* (Oxford University Press, 2023) 27; N El-Enany (2015) 869.

³ V Guiraudon, ‘European Integration and Migration Policy’ (2000) 38 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 255.

⁴ D Thym (2023) 27.

⁵ See E Guild, *Immigration Law in the European Community* (Kluwer, 2001) 255–273; K Hailbronner, *Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy of the European Union* (Kluwer, 2000) 47–52.

⁶ D Thym (2023) 27.

⁷ V Guiraudon (2000) 255; D Thym (2023) 27.

⁸ See Articles 61–69 of the EC Treaty (Treaty of Amsterdam).

⁹ D Thym (2023) 28.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² S Peers, ‘EU Justice and Home Affairs’ in P Craig and G de Búrca (eds.) *The Evolution of EU Law* 2nd edn (Oxford University Press, 2011) 276; A Wallerman Ghavanini, A Östlund, C Pedersen, S Kaddar, and I Karahan,

Together, these changes have redefined the balance of EU and national power, significantly strengthening the role of EU institutions in shaping migration law and policy. The Treaty changes place migration under the Commission's agenda-setting power, co-legislation by the Council and Parliament, and judicial review by the CJEU. Migration policy is a shared competence, meaning that Member States are precluded from legislating in areas where the EU has already acted.¹³ While Member States may adopt more protective standards in areas governed by minimum harmonisation, they must not compromise the effectiveness of EU law. This follows from the principle of sincere cooperation and the primacy of EU law.

2 Internal Governance

EU migration law contains two dimensions: an internal and external. The internal dimension comprises legal instruments on migration that harmonises national regulations. It includes directives and regulations on the asylum procedure, refugee definition, reception conditions, and Member State responsibility. The external, by contrast, concerns the EU's relation with third countries. A main part of the external dimension are readmission agreements. This section discusses the EU's authority in regulating entry and movements of third-country nationals into the EU. Section 2.1 outlines the EU's competences and section 2.2 describes key legislation in the area of migration and asylum law.

2.1 Internal competences

EU internal migration competences concern its authority to harmonise national regulation of the entry and residence of third-country nationals. These competences are set out in Articles 77–79 TFEU.

Article 77 TFEU governs border management. It outlines three policy aims for EU migration law. These are: (1) ensuring the absence of any controls on persons, whatever their nationality, when crossing internal borders; (2) conducting checks on persons and effectively monitoring the crossing of external borders; (3) gradually implementing an integrated system for the management of external borders. Article 77 TFEU demonstrates the connection between internal and external migration law. While there is a constitutional objective of removing checks of migrants crossing the internal borders of the EU, the EU aims to reinforce the external border checks of third-country nationals.

On this basis, the European Parliament and the Council are competent to adopt measures concerning the common policy on visas and other short-stay residence permits; the checks on persons crossing external borders, the conditions under which third-country nationals can travel within the EU for a short period; the necessary measures for establishing an integrated management system for external borders; and the absence of control of persons crossing the internal borders.

Article 77(3) TFEU also states that 'if action by the Union should prove necessary to facilitate the exercise of the right referred to in Article 20(2)(a), and if the Treaties have not provided the necessary powers', the Council may act under a special legislative procedure to adopt provisions concerning passports, identity cards, residence permits, or other such documents. The Council shall in this case act unanimously after consulting the European Parliament. Article 77(4) TFEU clarifies that the internal competences under Article 77 TFEU

¹³ 'An Empirical Approach to Separation of Powers Research in the EU: Introducing the SepaRope Judiciary Dataset' (2022) *CERGU Working Paper Series*.

¹³ Article 4(2) TFEU.

do not affect the competence of the Member States concerning the geographical demarcation of their borders.

Article 78 TFEU provides the basis for the EU's asylum policy. The EU has wide and far-reaching competences within this area. It is authorised to adopt a uniform status of asylum and subsidiary protection for third-country nationals, which is valid throughout the Union; a common system of temporary protection for displaced persons in the event of a massive inflow; common procedures for the granting and withdrawing of uniform asylum or subsidiary protection status; the criteria and mechanisms for determining Member State responsibility for asylum or subsidiary protection application; standards concerning the conditions for the reception of applicants for asylum or subsidiary protection.

Article 79 TFEU provides a wider range of internal competences concerning migration, asylum, and border controls. It states that the EU may adopt measures regarding the conditions of entry and residence, standards on the issue by Member States of long-term visas and residence permits, including those for the purpose of family reunification; the definition of the rights of third-country nationals.

Long-term visas have not, however, been harmonised at EU level. This was the gist of a ruling issued during the migration crisis. In the case *X and X*, the CJEU ruled that the Visa Code only covers intended stays of no more than 90 days.¹⁴ The CJEU emphasised that the EU has not yet harmonised long-term visas, which is why an application for a visa to later apply for asylum falls outside the scope of the Visa Code and EU law. The CJEU thus lacked jurisdiction to delve deeper into the meaning of 'humanitarian visa'.

Notably, a key area where EU competence remains limited is the integration of third-country nationals. Under Article 79(4) TFEU, the European Parliament and the Council are competent to adopt measures that encourage and support Member States actions aimed at fostering integration. However, the provision explicitly excludes any harmonisation of national laws in this policy area. As a result, integration policy remains under the exclusive control of individual Member States. Additionally, Article 79(5) TFEU affirms that Member States retain full discretion over setting the number of third-country nationals they admit for employment or self-employment purposes.

Furthermore, there are international law obligations limiting the political autonomy in migration. Article 78(1) TFEU requires that the EU's asylum policy complies with international legal frameworks, specifically the 1951 Geneva Convention on the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol, along with other relevant international agreements. Article 6 TEU holds that the rights within the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (CFR) possess the same legal status as the Treaties. This imposes constraints on migration lawmaking. Several CFR provisions are relevant in this context, such as the right to life (Article 2), the prohibition of torture and inhuman or degrading treatment (Article 4), the right to liberty and security (Article 6), respect for private and family life (Article 7), the prohibition of refoulement (Article 19(2)), and the rights of the child, which include the requirement that a child's best interests must be a primary consideration (Article 24).

Human rights are fundamental principles in EU law; however, their definition and scope remain ambiguous and requires further clarification in secondary legislation and case law. For example, the right to liberty and security limits the power to detain asylum seekers but leaves out the details for detention, such as time limits and the grounds for detention. This leaves room for the EU to define migration rights. The Treaty provisions also indicate the EU's willingness

¹⁴ Case C-638/16 PPU *X and X v Belgium* ECLI:EU:C:2017:173.

to assume a lawmaking role within the confines of human rights. Alongside its commitment to human rights, the EU emphasises migration control and the fight against irregular migration. For instance, Article 79 TFEU calls for the adoption of ‘enhanced measures to combat illegal immigration’, and Article 77 TFEU highlight the need for ‘efficient monitoring of the crossing of external borders’.

This legal framework creates a complex constitutional framework. The Treaties aspire to uphold a human rights-based approach to migration, yet simultaneously responds to collective concerns about border management and migration control. The broad and sometimes conflicting objectives set out in the Treaties suggest that the EU has not adopted a definitive normative stance on migration. Instead, it reflects competing narratives within European migration discourse: on one side, security and control; on the other, human rights and humanitarian responsibility. These tensions call for a carefully balanced legislative approach. In the absence of a clear constitutional instruction, EU institutions retain broad discretion in shaping migration law. The EU’s far-reaching internal competences enhance the power of its institutions relative to national authorities.

2.2 Internal migration law and policy

The EU has enacted a number of legal acts regulating the entry and stay of third country nationals. These legal instruments address the situation of asylum seekers, workers, students, family members, and those without legal status. EU migration law can be divided into three main areas: asylum, legal migration, and border controls.

The first area, asylum, concerns issues such as the application procedure, the scope of international protection, and the standards for reception of asylum seekers. The procedure is mainly governed by the Asylum Procedures Directive¹⁵ and the Dublin III Regulation.¹⁶

The Asylum Procedures Directive sets out common rules for handling applications in each Member State.¹⁷ Article 3 states that applications can be ‘made in the territory, including that the border, in the territorial waters or in the transit zones of the Member States’. Article 6 establishes time limits for registration of asylum applications, Article 9 guarantees the right to remain in the Member State while the application is examined, and Article 12 outlines key safeguard such as access to information, interpretation, and legal assistance. These provisions are central to ensuring the right to asylum across the EU.¹⁸

The Dublin III Regulation determines which Member State is responsible for examining an application. Article 13 provides that responsibility lies with the first Member State ‘irregularly crossed’. The CJEU clarified this concept in the *AS* and *Jafari* cases, holding that any border crossing that does not meet the legal entry requirements is considered irregular.¹⁹ Although this

¹⁵ Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (Asylum Procedures Directive) [2013] OJ L 180/60.

¹⁶ Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the Member States by a third-country national or a stateless person (Dublin III Regulation) [2013] OJ L 180/31.

¹⁷ Note that from 12 June 2026, the Asylum Procedures Directive is replaced by the new Asylum Procedures Regulation (see Regulation (EU) 2024/1348 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 establishing a common procedure for international protection in the Union and repealing Directive 2013/32/EU).

¹⁸ See eg Case C-808/18 *European Commission v Hungary* ECLI:EU:C:2020:1029; Case C-823/21 *European Commission v Hungary* ECLI:EU:C:2023:504; Case C-72/22 *PPU MA and Valstybės sienos apsaugos tarnyba* ECLI:EU:C:2022:505.

¹⁹ Joined Cases C-490/16 *AS v Republika Slovenija* ECLI:EU:C:2017:585 and C-646/16 *Khadija Jafari and Zainab Jafari* ECLI:EU:C:2017:586.

system places disproportionate responsibility on border states, the Court declined to explore any alternative system of responsibility based on the principle of solidarity under Article 80 TFEU. Notably, the Dublin principle remains in the new Asylum and Migration Management Regulation (AMMR).²⁰ While the Dublin principle remains, a broad set of options are introduced for Member States to improve the solidarity within the asylum system. The new framework enables Member States to choose between relocations, financial contributions, operational support, and request deductions.

Rules on the granting of international protection, including refugee status and subsidiary protection, are contained in the Qualification Directive.^{21,22} It defines ‘persecution’, identifies actors of protection, and regulates when refugee status may be refused or withdrawn. By covering subsidiary protection, it extends beyond the Refugee Convention to safeguard those facing serious harm without qualifying as refugees. The Asylum Procedures Directive (Article 3) and the Qualification Directive (Articles 20 – 35) provide a broad protection against non-refoulement, covering access to determination procedure for everyone irrespective of a real risk of refoulement.²³ Notably, while Article 33(2) Refugee Convention allows exceptions to non-refoulement in cases of national sovereignty, the Qualification Directive is more protective, prohibiting in absolute terms the return of a refugee facing torture or inhuman treatment.²⁴

Standards for the treatment of asylum seekers are found in the Reception Conditions Directive.²⁵ Its purpose is to ensure a dignified standard of living for asylum seekers in the EU and prevent secondary movements. Studies have shown that reception conditions can influence migration movements.²⁶ Harmonisation is thus intended to limit the incentives to choose Member State on the basis of reception conditions. The Directive regulates access to housing, health care, education for minors, and the labour market for asylum seekers. It covers anyone who has applied for asylum and Member State are obligated to provide reception conditions for as long as the asylum seeker is allowed to remain.

²⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/1351 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May on asylum and migration management, amending Regulations (EU) 2021/1147 and (EU) 2021/1060 and repealing Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 OJ L 2024/1351.

²¹ Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted (Qualification Directive) [2011] OJ L 337/9.

²² The Qualification Directive is being replaced by the new Qualification Regulation (see Regulation (EU) 2024/1347 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection and for the content of the protection granted, amending Council Directive 2003/109/EC and repealing Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, OJ L 2024/1347). Notable changes are stricter rules on secondary movements, for example, the five-year waiting period for long-term resident status for beneficiaries of international protection will restart if they are found in a Member State where they are not permitted to stay. The Regulation also introduces compulsory review to assess changes in countries of origin.

²³ See D Thym, *European Migration Law* (Oxford University Press, 2023) 354.

²⁴ Joined Cases C-391/16, C-77/17, and C-78/17 *M v Ministerstvo vnitra and X and X v Commissaire général aux réfugiés et aux apatrides* ECLI:EU:C:2019:403 [96].

²⁵ Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (Reception Conditions Directive [2013] OJ L 180/96. Note that this Directive is being replaced by a recast Reception Conditions Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/1346 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection).

²⁶ D Thym (2023) 410.

The Temporary Protection Directive departs from this asylum framework.²⁷ It is designed to provide swift, collective protection to refugees in situations where the ordinary asylum system might collapse under pressure. Unlike the individualised asylum procedure, the Directive offers immediate access to protection without case-by-case assessment, contingent on a political decision that a ‘mass influx’ is taking place.²⁸ The Directive was established in 2001 but only activated first in 2022, to grant immediate protection to Ukrainian refugees fleeing Russia’s full-scale invasion.

The second subfield, regular migration, relates to categories such as family reunification,²⁹ visas,³⁰ employment,³¹ and study. This type of migration requires prior authorisation, meaning that individuals must obtain visas or residence permits before arriving in a Member State. The Family Reunification Directive, adopted under Article 79 TFEU, establishes family reunification as an EU objective. The Directive contains both protective and restrictive elements, as the right to family reunification can be made subject to various conditions, including income requirements, course fees, language and integration tests, and age limits, which allow Member States to reject applications.³² The scope for national restrictions have been clarified in a series of landmark rulings. In its rulings, the Court has framed family reunification as a clear right and precluded Member States from making family reunification difficult.³³

The third, and final subfield, external border management, encompasses migration control measures and responses to irregular migration. This includes pre-entry screening, border surveillance, detention, and readmission agreements. Key legislative instruments are the Schengen Borders Code,³⁴ the Frontex Regulation,³⁵ and the Return Directive.³⁶ Notably, a mandatory border procedure will be introduced in June 2026 for asylum applicants who are unlikely to receive asylum, may mislead the authorities, or present a security risk.³⁷ The Return Directive enshrines the right to liberty and security and has helped protect migrants from arbitrary detention. The CJEU has found, on the basis of the instrument, that detention must be

²⁷ Council Directive 2001/55/EC of July 2001 on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof, OJ L 212/12.

²⁸ Article 5 Temporary Protection Directive.

²⁹ Council Directive 2003/86/EC of 22 September 2003 on the right to family reunification (Family Reunification Directive) [2003] OJ L 251/12.

³⁰ Regulation (EC) No 810/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a Community Code on Visas (Visa Code) [2009] OJ L 243/1.

³¹ Directive 2021/1883 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2021 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purpose of highly qualified employment [2021] OJ L 382/1.

³² See Articles 6 and 7 of the Family Reunification Directive.

³³ See eg Case C-578/08 *Rimou Chakroun v Minister van Buitenlandse Zaken* ECLI:EU:C:2010:117; Case C-558/14 *Khachab v Subdelegación del Gobierno en Álava* ECLI:EU:C:2016:285; Case C-550/16 *A and S v Staatssecretaris van Veiligheid en Justitie* ECLI:EU:C:2018:248; Case C-153/14 *Minister van Buitenlandse Zaken v K and A* ECLI:EU:C:2015:453.

³⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/399 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on a Union Code on the rules governing the movement of persons across borders (Schengen Borders Code) [2016] OJ L 77/1.

³⁵ Regulation (EU) 2019/1896 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 November 2019 on the European Border and Coast Guard and repealing Regulations (EU) NO 1052/2013 and (EU) 2016/1624 OJ L 295/1.

³⁶ Directive 2008/115 EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals (Return Directive) [2008] OJ L 384/98. The Directive is being replaced by

³⁷ Regulation (EU) 2024/1439 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 establishing a return border procedure, and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1148 OJ L 2024/1349.

necessary and proportionate, subject to judicial review, and limited to the period during which the grounds for detention remain valid.³⁸

In recent years, the EU has increasingly focused on improving immigration control. The Pact on Migration and Asylum demonstrates this development. A notable part of the reform program is the Crisis and Force Majeure Regulation.³⁹ It enables Member States to close their borders to asylum seekers when the situation is characterised as a crisis, mass influx, or force majeure. This opportunity is likely to be attractive to Member States who seek to limit migration, but certain safeguards apply. The Regulation only applies in ‘exceptional’ situations and fundamental principles of EU primary law apply, including the proportionality principle. This is needed as the Regulation significantly impacts the right to asylum (Article 18 EU Charter), the principle of non-refoulement (Article 4 EU Charter), the right to liberty and security (Article 6 EU Charter), protection in the event of removal, and expulsion or extradition (Article 19 EU Charter), the rights of child (Article 24 EU Charter). Overall, EU asylum law is changing to make returns more effective and improve border management and control.

3 External Governance: Competences and Policies

The external dimension of migration law is an increasingly important part of EU migration governance. Increasing migration flows have led to a stronger emphasis on border security. To limit migration, there has been a shift in migration policies and decision-making. The executive is getting more powerful, as intergovernmental negotiations and informal agreements increasingly take precedence. Externalisation strategies – such as readmission agreements, mobility partnerships, and cooperation with third countries – have strengthened the executive.

The EU’s external competences in migration law are concerned with how the Union may engage with third countries on migration-related issues. There are two Treaty provisions outlining the EU’s external competences in migration. Article 78(2)(g) states that the EU is competent to adopt measures comprising ‘partnership and cooperation with third countries for the purpose of managing inflows of people applying for asylum or subsidiary or temporary protection’. Article 79(3) TFEU states that the EU ‘may conclude agreements with third countries for the readmission to their countries of origin or provenance of third-country nationals who do not or who no longer fulfil the conditions for entry, presence or residence in the territory of one of the Member States’.

The EU external migration policy operates along three axes: broader strategic frameworks, control and return, and partnerships. First, strategic frameworks provide the objectives and priorities for EU external policy. The Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (GAMM), adopted in 2005 and later revised in 2011, provides an overarching framework for EU external migration policy. Its four objectives are: improving the organisation of legal migration, preventing irregular migration, strengthening the synergies between migration and development, and strengthening international protection systems.⁴⁰ More recently, the Migration Pact adopted in 2024 has further reinforced the external dimension of migration law by making cooperation with third countries a central priority.

³⁸ Cases C-924/19 PPU and C-925/19 PPU *FMS and Others v Országos Idegenrendesszeti Főigazgatóság Dél-alföldi Regionális Igazgatóság and Országos Idegenrendesszeti Főigazgatóság* [2020] ECLI:EU:C:2020:367.

³⁹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1359 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 addressing situations of crisis and force majeure in the field of migration and asylum and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1147.

⁴⁰ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (COM/2011/0743 final).

The control and return axis includes readmission agreements, and arrangements and cooperations with third countries. The procedure to conclude readmission agreements is outlined in Article 218 TFEU: the Council opens negotiations, adopts negotiating directives, authorises the signing of agreements, nominates the negotiator, and concludes them, while the Commission conducts negotiations. The Parliament must be informed during the process and give its consent to the conclusion of agreements.

In practice, however, the Commission and the Council increasingly rely on non-binding, informal readmission arrangements outside Treaty procedures, thereby excluding Parliament.⁴¹ The Joint Declaration on Migration Cooperation between Afghanistan and the EU states, for instance, that it is ‘not intended to create legal rights or obligations under international or domestic law’.⁴² Similarly, the EU-Turkey Statement was adopted without a formal decision to authorise the opening of negotiations with Turkey according to Article 218(2) TFEU and the text was never submitted to the European Parliament for approval under Articles 294(2) and 218(6) TFEU. The CJEU subsequently found that the Statement was not an EU act but a political declaration by the Member States in their own capacity, and therefore outside the Court’s jurisdiction.⁴³

Beyond formal and informal readmission arrangements, the EU pursues a wider set of partnerships with third countries to manage migration. The 2016 Partnership Framework on Migration linked cooperation on returns and border management to development policy.⁴⁴ Under this framework, migration compacts were negotiated with countries such as Libya, Niger, Nigeria, Mali, Ethiopia, and Senegal. Financial instruments, including the EU Emergency Trust for Africa,⁴⁵ and more recently, the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI – Global Europe), channel significant funding to address so-called ‘root causes’ of migration, and strengthen border controls.⁴⁶

The growing reliance on informal measures has increasingly replaced formal instruments and sidelining the competent EU institutions in the process. This trend reflects a significant shift in power from the legislative and judicial branches to the executive. Informalisation bypasses the European Parliament’s right to be consulted and circumvents the scrutiny of the CJEU. The external migration policy comes in the form of agreements, mobility partnerships, and broad policy programmes. Thus, measures are taken at EU level by Member States but outside the formal procedures and competences outlined in the Treaties. Ultimately, while the EU possesses sufficient external competences to make international agreements, these are overlooked or bypassed for political reasons.

⁴¹ D Gnes and M Sormunen, ‘No Appetite for Conflict? Assessing How the European Parliament and the European Ombudsman Engage with Executive Discretion in Informalised EU Readmission Policy’ in C Eckes, P Leino-Sandberg, and A Wallerman Ghavanini (eds.) *The Dynamics of Powers in the European Union* (Hart Publishing, 2024) 56.

⁴² See Joint Declaration on Migration Cooperation between Afghanistan and the EU [2021] at https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/jmcd_-_english_version_signed_26apr2021.pdf.

⁴³ Cases T-192/16 *NF v European Council* ECLI:EU:T:2017:128; T-193/16 *NG v European Council* ECLI:EU:T:2017:129; and T-257/16 *NM v European Council* ECLI:EU:T:2017:130. References are made to the Case T-192/16 *NF v European Council* ECLI:EU:T:2017:128.

⁴⁴ European Commission, *Communication on establishing a new Partnership Framework with third countries under the European Agenda on Migration*, COM(2016) 385 final, 7 June 2016.

⁴⁵ European Commission, *EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF for Africa)* 2015.

⁴⁶ European Commission, *Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument – Global Europe (NDICI – Global Europe)* 2021.

4 Conclusion

EU migration law embodies a complex constitutional structure marked by several competing interests: integration vs. sovereignty, human rights vs. control, supranationalism vs. intergovernmentalism. The Treaties empower EU institutions to legislate extensively in migration but does not articulate a normative vision. As a result, EU migration policy evolves within a framework of legal ambiguity and political contestation with ongoing recalibration between different values and interests.

The evolution of EU migration law illustrates a gradual but marked shift from national sovereignty towards increased supranational governance. Initially constrained by intergovernmentalism and unanimity, the EU's role was limited to supporting the Member States. Successive Treaty reforms have progressively expanded the EU's competences. Today, migration is a shared competence shaped through Commission agenda-setting, co-legislation by the Council and European Parliament, and judicial oversight by the CJEU.

The EU's migration competences can be divided into three subfields. The first is regular migration, which covers issues relating to family reunification, workers, and students. Regular migration is pre-authorised, meaning that the migrants obtain permits before entering any Member State of the EU. The second is asylum, covering issues such as asylum procedures, definition and scope of asylum protection, and reception conditions. The third subfield is external border controls, an umbrella term for migration control and measures tackling irregular migration. It involves pre-entry checks, territorial oversight, detentions, and return agreements.

Certain limitations remain. Integration policy remains largely outside the EU's legislative reach, and Member States retain control over the volume of migrants admitted. Furthermore, EU migration policy is constrained by international human rights obligations. These rights leave, however, room for interpretation and political manoeuvre.

In the external dimension, the EU is competent to conclude binding agreements with third countries. Yet in practice, informal arrangements have increasingly replaced formal agreements, circumventing Treaty-based procedures. The EU-Turkey Statement is a prominent example. This trend undermines transparency and accountability and shifts power towards executive actors.